

Tracing More-than-Human Histories in Andean Rural Landscapes.

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False conservation dichotomies emerging from a drying highland lake

“As a minority group, we are not taken into account” (leader Vilañeque, 25 August 2023).¹ Those were the words by one of the Indigenous leaders of the Uru Nation, recognised as one of Bolivia’s ethnic minorities, during a meeting at the Constitutional Court in Sucre. The ‘Uru of Lake Poopó’ form a sub-group that lives, dispersed in three tiny communities (Puñaka Tinta María, Vilañeque, and Llapallapani), on the shores of what was once a vast lake. Lake Poopó, or *Qota Mama* or “Mother Lake” (see figure 1), constitutes the source of their livelihood and the centre of their cosmovision. Over the last decades, Bolivia’s second largest lake has been rapidly shrinking into a salty puddle.

Figure 1. Indigenous authorities preparing to perform the yearly ritual for the Qota Mama on Lake Poopó, August 2022 (photograph by the author).

“The lake was our food, our territory, the study room for our kids,” the leader continued (25 August 2023). A group of Uru authorities had gathered in the country’s constitutional capital to pressure authorities to support the reconstitution of their territory, which is being lost to severe desertification. Known as *Qot Zuñi* or “the people of the lake”, the Uru people that inhabited the lake basin organise their lives on and around the lake as fishers and hunter-gatherers of aquatic birds and their eggs. As will become clear throughout this article, the state as well as neighbouring, more agriculture-oriented communities have instrumentalised this intimate relation with the lake since colonial times, portraying the Uru as confined to the lake in order to gain control over the Uru population and deny their historical rights to the land.

As the lake is undergoing irreversible changes, and with very limited access to land, the Uru are at risk of becoming climate refugees, deprived from water and land. In response, the communities of Lake Poopó have initiated a negotiation process with the government to obtain land rights, as the basis for a sustainable future within the lake basin. However, as magistrates at the Constitutional Court

¹ All names of have been anonymised.

pointed out, the Uru territory overlaps with the lake basin's status as a protected area. Despite the fact that all studies, proposals and procedures to bring the area under environmental protection explicitly recognise Uru culture as a constitutional part of this landscape, their control over land continues to be framed as incompatible. Hence, recurring dichotomies between Uru territorial control and land and conservation regimes continue to hamper the Uru people's future within their historical territory.

While the Uru's historical and contemporary struggles deserve a more detailed study (Wachtel 2001; Barra/Lara/Coca 2011; De Munter/Quintero/Rocha 2019; Cottyn 2023), this article aims to outline a broader analytical framework to historicise apparent incompatibilities emerging from contemporary conservation schemes. Today's multiple, planetary-wide crises are exposing in ever more explicit ways the limits of conventional environmental governance practices that seek to protect nature by enclosing it (Büscher/Fletcher 2019). Suggesting a tension, even incompatibility between 'inhabited' and 'natural' landscapes, such practices tend to exclude or simplify other – including indigenous – modes and practices of relating to nature. The contradictions that currently keep the Uru communities from securing their territorial rights within a drastically transformed landscape are steeped in colonial-capitalist dichotomies that tend to separate "Human" society from a univocal "Nature" that can be controlled and commodified (Doyon/Vacarro 2019; Moore 2015). In response, local communities, scholars, practitioners and activists are increasingly pushing for a paradigm shift, based on an understanding that human and nonhuman lives co-produce the landscapes they inhabit through multispecies or "more-than-human" histories (O'Gorman/Gaynor 2020). Inspired by this emerging paradigm shift, I am interested in examining how the more-than-human entanglements that shape specific Andean rural landscapes have been subjected to, and responded to exclusionary dichotomous schemes over the last two centuries.

From this interest in more-than-human histories in the Andean highlands emerged the interdisciplinary research project "HI-LANDeS. More-than-Human Histories of Rural Landscapes in the Andes, 19th-20th century."² Combining archival research and ethnographic action-research, the project aims to trace the intimate and historically shifting entanglements between human communities, water bodies, animals, plants and other lives that inhabit two Andean wetland areas - the mentioned Lake Poopó basin south from the city of Oruro, and the Lauca-Sajama basin (within the Coipasa basin) on the Chilean-Bolivian border (see map 1). Both (sub)basins are part of the international altiplano basin that interconnects Lake Titicaca with the southern salt flats; the so-called TDPS system.

Through the project, I make the case for a historicizing and entangled perspective towards landscape transformations, thereby exploring how the writing of "more-than-human" landscape histories can inform contemporary governance challenges in rural societies. In the following, I first discuss the conceptual outlines and ambitions of this project. I then return to Lake Poopó, which forms one of the project's two central case studies, to briefly illustrate the ongoing research. I close with some final reflections on what role rural history can play in contemporary efforts towards more inclusive environmental governance practices.

² HI-LANDeS is an individual postdoctoral research project, based at the History Department of Ghent University, Belgium. I am developing the research in collaboration with the History and Geography department at the Universidad de Tarapacá (Arica, Chile), the Bolivian environmental NGOs Agua Sustentable (La Paz) and Centro de Ecología y Pueblos Andinos (Oruro), the Uru communities of the Lake Poopó basin, and the Aymara communities of Sajama.

Map 1. The Lake Poopó basin (light grey area) and the Lauca-Sajama sub-basin within the Lake Coipasa basin (white area) form the research area of the HI-LANDeS project. Map elaborated by Hans Blomme (Ghent University).

Andean wetlands as a laboratory for rethinking landscape as concept and practice

The last years mark a growing interest within social sciences and humanities research in revisiting the concept of landscape from a political ecology and ontological perspective (Howard et al. 2013; Olwig 2016; Tsing/Mathews/Bubandt 2019; Perlik 2019). Whereas ‘landscape’ used to be deployed as a quantifiable entity that forms the passive background to social change, this interdisciplinary interrogation has allowed for a much more dynamic understanding of landscape as a mode of seeing, knowing and doing, and as actively involved in social change – landscape as practice and participant in world-making processes. However, as the notion of ‘landscape’ also (re)gains importance with in environmental governance, Bluwstein has pointed out how the “landscape approach” relies on a much more fixed idea of landscape that allows to depoliticize and abstract complex human-nature entanglements (Bluwstein 2021; see also Haller/Branca 2022). He consequently insists that the growing critique to “decolonise” conservation requires a critical rethinking of the landscape concept.

Strategic sites for carbon storage, water sources, and biodiversity, as well as home to resilient indigenous communities, the Andean highlands constitute a particularly provocative and productive site for such exercise. As Briceño and Coronado (2019) explain, the Andes offer a clear illustration of how the landscape concept historically has been instrumentalised to frame and abstract space into a blank canvas for capitalist incorporation. Especially since the late 19th century, the landscape concept was appropriated as a “means of accumulation” (2019: 14). In a context of commodity booms and expanding state power, Andean cultural landscapes were presented as obstacles to development. Cadastres, cartography and photography provided new tools to access and reorganise these culturally and bio-diverse spaces in terms of ‘natural resources’ that can be extracted through modern mining and agricultural projects. The research area of the HI-LANDeS project constitutes a historical core area of

the mining and metallurgy industry – silver in colonial times, and tin since the late 19th century. Most mines and processing plants continue to be situated near the city of Oruro and to the east of Lake Poopó, discharging their waste waters directly into the lake. The Lauca-Sajama area is mainly oriented towards camelid herding, which used to form the basis of the area's insertion as an essential transport link in the global mining commodity chain, and is today oriented towards national wool and meat markets. The Poopó basin became the site of a fishing industry boom (and bust) in the second half of the twentieth century, and was incorporated into the quinoa boom in the early 21st century.

More recently, in the face of new challenges linked to climate change and biodiversity loss, the Andean highlands, and especially the wetlands of the cold and extremely arid Central Andean ecoregion of the *puna*, have attracted new research and policy interests. In this context, Andean wetlands are being reframed by scientists, national governments and international conservation agencies as 'strategic' areas for the storage of CO₂, water regulation, and preserving biodiversity. This 'strategic' quality reflects a more critical approach towards the environmental impacts of natural resource extraction in wetlands, yet this reframing tends to largely pit conservation goals against local livelihoods.³ As recent research in Andean wetland areas demonstrate, contemporary conservation discourses and policies still tend to reproduce unequal power relations that increase the vulnerability and foreclose the participation of indigenous, peasant, and other local communities in wetland conservation (e.g. García/Prieto/Kalazich 2020; Perreault 2020). As O'Gorman stresses in her research on the wetlands of Australia's Murray-Darling Basin,

“old debates about development versus preservation, culture versus nature, do not capture the complex histories and contemporary realities of these areas, and indeed are having adverse effects on them. New ways of understanding, managing, and relating to wetlands [...] are urgently needed. [...] The place to begin is a recognition that wetlands in the basin are rich not only in diverse kinds of plants, animals, and insects but also in human histories.” (O'Gorman 2021: 6).

While the Andean highlands are explicitly recognised and celebrated as the cradle of major indigenous cultures, the installation of protected areas tends to mould and valorise these landscapes into empty, disconnected spaces with a static past (De Marchi 2020). Current efforts by scientist and international organisations such as the UN to integrate “traditional ecological knowledge” (TEK) in environmental research and governance seem to counter this trend by recognising indigenous and other local communities as key knowledge producers. However, these efforts risk to be neutralised by the drive to streamline such complex knowledge systems within Western scientific and management frameworks (Cruikshank 2005; Nelson/Shilling 2018). Rather, as Cruikshank asserts, these knowledges need to be approached in terms of “socially situated” and “porous” practices informed by historical encounters with humans and their (colonial-capitalist) projects, and with landscapes (2005: 10). By involving local communities and organisations, HI-LANDeS seeks to follow this critical approach, placing local knowledges centre stage while critically interrogating their dynamic attunement to regional ecologies and histories. Through participatory historical research it also attempts to respond to recent interdisciplinary Andean wetland research that stresses the importance of gaining an enhanced historical understanding of environmental transformation processes (García/Prieto/Kalazich 2020; Yager et al. 2019). Thereto, it builds on Andean Studies' rich tradition in historical rural sociology and ethnohistory (Platt 1982; Stern 1987; Larson et al. 1995; Wachtel 2001; Ferreira/Isbell 2016; Puente 2022). It integrates nuanced insights into rural communities' repertoires of reaction towards state and market expansion with a more-than-human perspective to analyse how these repertoires equally integrate different ways of knowing and relating to non-human entities and landscape transformations. New environmental humanities research, particularly as this field is emerging in Latin America (Cadena 2015; Blackmore/Heffes 2022; Carvalho Cabral 2024), offer evidence on how local communities have actively shaped, and been shaped by not only the political and socio-economic structures but also the landscapes within which they organise their lives in negotiation with other, non-human inhabitants of those landscapes.

What emerges is a concept of landscape as the historical, spatially and temporarily unstable product of a constant process of “making and growing” (Hallam/Ingold 2014) through communities' adaptive potential and multispecies entanglements. Geographers Cisani et al. (2022) capture this inherent

³ For a discussion of how the ecosystem concept has informed a similar reframing, and consequent tensions with local rural communities, in the páramos of the Colombian Andes, see Martínez et al. 2024.

instability and mobility of landscapes by referring to “unruly landscapes”. The same notion of unruliness transpires in anthropologists Tsing, Mathews and Bubandt’s concept of “patchy Anthropocene landscape” (2019), with patchiness resulting from the way in which state- and market-driven reorganisations to “simplify” landscapes into smooth and controllable constructs are repeatedly undermined by unexpected multispecies responses. In the Andes, such attempts at simplifying the landscape intensified from the mid-19th century onwards in the context of the continent’s “second conquest” (Topik/Wells 1997). Historical research has documented rural communities’ resistance, negotiation and pragmatic adjustment to new legal, economic and material infrastructures that sought to enclose rural lands, discipline rural labour, and assimilate rural life to modern citizenship values (Larson 2004). Yet, the landscape often tends to feature only as a passive, fixed backdrop of the social changes under study. HI-LANDeS seeks to assess the repercussions of commodity booms and liberalism of the late 19th century on rural Andean landscapes, and of successive cycles of (attempted) landscape simplification during the following century. The project is particularly interested in the frictions such state- or market-induced landscape reorganisations produced with local communities’ landscape-shaping practices that are attuned to, and support the unstable character of wetland ecologies.

Combining archival sources and multispecies ethnography (Kirksey/Helmreich 2010), the project develops a set of wetland case studies that demonstrate how expanding state- and market-oriented infrastructures (extractive industries, roads and border regimes, protected areas) have materialised in changing patterns and practices of communal land and water control. These historical-anthropological case studies start from the vantage point of specific non-human companions or “allies” of local communities in the process of inhabiting these wetlands, thereby interrelating these shifting multispecies entanglements with new dynamics in intra- and interethnic conflict, socio-economic integration or exclusion, and political empowerment or marginalisation. The already mentioned Lake Poopó basin (Bolivia) constitutes one of the research areas, and will be developed further in the next section.

Interwoven Uru-lake histories: Knowing, surviving, and resisting beyond land-water dichotomies

Lake Poopó is a shallow lake situated in an endorheic watershed, which means its waters have no outlet to external bodies of water. Its shallowness makes it susceptible to cyclical changes, with small fluctuations in its volume – due to climate variability or irrigation withdrawals (Lima-Quispe et al. 2021) - producing considerable transformations. Variations in wind, precipitation, and water inflow easily translate into stark changes of lake’s extension, as well as its shape, depth, and location.⁴ Its isolation from the ocean makes it very vulnerable to the growing water demands and pollution. While water easily evaporates in this semi-desert climate, the remaining lake content accumulates large quantities of sediments from nearby mining operations, urbanisation and expanding agricultural activities. Together with climate change and recent diversions in the rivers that provide the lake’s main water intake, these growing pressures result in an acceleration of the region’s natural process of salinisation, and hence the lake’s desertification.

Recent interventions, including the lake’s designation as a wetland conservation site under the international Ramsar convention⁵ (Rocha 2002) and large EU investments⁶ to improve the water basin’s management, have failed to prevent that this area of over 2000 km² continues to convert into a marshy salt pan. As anthropologists have observed, most scientific responses to the lake’s disappearance tend to reduce this transformation to a quantifiable decrease in water volume, equating

⁴ Low water levels lead to water scarcity and a considerable shrinking of the lake, negatively affecting the extent of *titora* reeds (*Schoenoplectus californicus*), which form essential breeding ground for fish and nesting sites for water birds.

⁵ In 2002, Lake Poopó and Lake Uru Uru (which is smaller, situated to the north of Poopó) were designated as sites for conservation under the Ramsar convention, a non-binding intergovernmental treaty for the protection and sustainable use of wetlands, especially for their importance as waterfowl habitat.

⁶ From 2010 to 2015, the European Union ran a 14 million euro investment programme for the conservation and rehabilitation of the Poopó basin. During the final year of the “Poopó Basin Program”, the lake suffered from a major drought, with the programme’s achievements unable to prevent or mitigate the lake’s transformation into a ‘puddle’ on the brink of completely disappearing (Vazquez 2018).

this loss of water with the loss of cultural practices (De Munter/Quiroga/Rocha 2019). Such approach overlooks that what is at stake are not separable amounts of water and cultural expressions, but the safeguarding of a complex interwoven assemblage in which not only humans and water, but also plants, animals, salt, pollution and spiritual ‘presences’ participate. Through fishing, hunting and gathering of aquatic birds and their eggs, weaving of *tatora* reeds into rafts and housing, and the navigation of the lake’s currents and reed bushes, the *Qot Zuñi* have developed profound knowledge about, and an intimate relationship of belonging with the lake. Rituals are dedicated to the *jalsuri* – the sacred underground springs that feed the lake – and the wind in order to renovate this Uru-lake interwovenness (Schwarz 1997:25). Uru practices express a dynamic attuning to the lake’s inherent variability, which allows them to cleverly exploit the seasonal cycles of the wind, *tatora* growth, bird nesting, and feather moulting.⁷

Through archival research, ethnographic field work, and collaborative work with the Uru communities as well as local NGO *Centro de Ecología y Pueblos Andinos* (Centre for Ecology and Andean Peoples, CEPA)⁸ in Oruro, I attempt to trace the historical colonial-capitalist dynamics that have sought to flatten and ‘fix’ this more-than-human watery landscape. Inspired by David Harvey’s notion (2001), such “fixes” can be traced in discursive and material interventions that have sought to subject these landscapes to rational management. As I will explain in the following, these interventions go back to early colonial reforms to optimise labour and resource extraction in the area by removing Uru families from the lake and its islands, and continued with the imposition of republican property regimes that excluded Uru lake-based families from access to land. More recent, 20th century environmental and infrastructural projects were equally justified in terms of the “development” of the lake and its population through “rational” management (Cottyn 2023). These reforms and projects have contributed to reframing of the landscape and its inhabitants in essentialist dualisms that confine land and water to separate physical, legal, and cultural spheres. As Schwarz has indicated (1996), these reorganisations have produced (often unintended) effects on the Uru’s material and symbolic relation in the Poopó water basin. .

However, with this project I am also interested in identifying how Uru families have actively responded to these state- and market-driven interventions and the multi-layered processes of exclusion they reproduce. By reading “against the grain”, historical sources reveal how they appropriated the lake and its fellow inhabitants – in particular *tatora* reeds – as strategic allies in their survival outside the reach of the state. Ethnohistorical research on colonial reorganisations has indicated how impoverished Uru families retreated to the lake as a way to stay outside the reach of the colonial state and the exploitative relations with other ethnic groups (Wachtel 1978; Barra/Lara/Coca 2011). While the Uru always had a strong relation to water bodies, this used to be combined with land-based activities, until early colonial changes incited a differentiation between more wealthy Uru assimilating with the land-based ethnic group of the Aymara,⁹ and poorer families being essentialised as an “inferior” ethnic group, left without land. . Both the desperate attempts of the colonial state to try to get the Uru out of the lake (Mendoza 1943), as well as the dispossession of Uru land by more agricultural-oriented communities in the area reflect the operation of a dichotomic vision on land as ‘civilised’ versus water representing ungovernability. The naturalisation (and interiorisation) of the Uru as “people of the lake” was seized as an excuse to erase the Uru’s historical land rights and gradually concealed how the lake had emerged as a strategy to cope with exclusion, land grabbing, and displacement.

In this project, I particularly focus on the intensification of this process from the 19th century onwards. Understudied archival records at the Judicial Archive of Poopó document how a context of new land legislation and climate changes triggered long and often violent cycles of conflict with non-Uru

⁷ Interviews by NGO Centro de Ecología y Pueblos Andinos, 2017; workshop by the author, 19 August 2022.

⁸ CEPA is a local, Bolivian organisation dedicated to socio-environmental justice and the rights of Indigenous Peoples. Since its foundation in 1995, it has worked closely with the Uru communities of Lake Poopó to support their rights as an ethnic minority group, and to give visibility to the effects of climate change and contamination on life in the Lake Poopó basin.

⁹ While the Uru are considered the oldest inhabitants of the Andean plateau, the Quechua and Aymara have become the most dominant ethnic population in this area of the altiplano – respectively the largest and second largest ethnic groups in contemporary Bolivia, and organised in several nations or “suyus”.

communities attempting to appropriate Uru territory (Mamani/Reyes 2005: 54-55). Those lawsuits as well as indigenous tax records kept at the National Archive in Sucre indicate how Uru groups in the Lake basin recurred to state instances to obtain official recognition of their recognition and historical rights. However, when new droughts in the first half of the 20th century eventually pushed the Uru communities out of the lake, they were left deprived of access to land, and increasingly subjected to semi-coerced labour relations.

Meanwhile, a historical review of scientific publications and of reports dispersed in libraries and the archives of the Oruro Regional Government and NGO CEPA give evidence of increasing scientific and policy interest to integrate the lake within the country's national economy throughout the 20th century. Schwarz has demonstrated how internationally financed development and infrastructure projects gradually introduced new exogenous governance concepts such as "sustainable development" and "environmental conservation" that prioritized the "rational use" of the lake's water resources (Schwarz 1996). While well-intended, these efforts to "save" the lake by neutralising its inherent variability required the prioritisation of certain practices and knowledges, and the delegitimation of other practices deemed irrational, in particular the so-called 'traditional' uses of the Uru. More recent source material, retrieved from newspaper archives, document how for instance the hunting of *pariwana* (flamingo birds) was actively criminalised into the 1990s.

The pattern that emerges from these successive interventions is one of simplification. By seeking to commensurate the lake's dynamics with decontextualised global development schemes, the lake was separated from a broader, more complex assemblage of interwoven lives and their unstable cycles. In doing so, local communities' knowledges, practices, and multispecies alliances to creatively adjust to highly unstable rhythms, often unpredictable transformations, and socio-economic inequalities that structure life in and around the lake were overlooked, and at times actively excluded or criminalised. It was not so much their relation with the lake itself that has been denied, but the fact that the Uru relation with the lake has never been straightforward, rather one of moving into, out, and with the lake, beyond exclusionary water-land dichotomies.

Closing reflections: What role can rural history play in generating more inclusive environmental governance practices?

Today, successive reorganisations have converted Lake Poopó into a dumpsite for urban and mining waste, a fishing zone taken over by non-native fish, a water source for mines and agriculture, and a protected area. The net result for the three small Uru communities that survived centuries-long discrimination is a restricted access to, and a broken alliance with the lake, its waters, its totora bushes, its fish and birds. In light of the broader ambitions of this project, initial insights from this history point to ways in which local communities have historically appropriated and co-constituted wetlands as mobile landscapes, yet in fragile and often contradictory ways. The landscape itself emerges from this and other case studies as companions and participants in, rather than fixed geographies of communities' histories.

This project also aims to address the epistemological, ethical and material implications of writing such "more-than-human" landscape histories. In bringing together archival documentation with oral histories, such histories evidence the tensions caused when local concerns, memories and knowledge remain underrepresented in conservation decision-making, and how this undermines efforts towards territorial and environmental justice. As part of the Uru's endeavour towards territorial reconstitution, I am currently accompanying leaders of the Uru communities in their consultation of archival documents that give evidence of the systematic dispossession they suffered. Through collective visits with the Indigenous authorities of the three Uru communities to regional and national archives (see figure 2), an online infrastructure for digitised sources, and a series of workshops, the project aims to co-create and co-curate a community archive. Through a collaboration with local stakeholders such as schools and social organisations, this collective practice can help to foster and transmit research capacity within the community over the longer term. Wary of any romanticisation, the HI-LANDeS project intends to develop instruments that can cultivate shared - even though uncomfortable - narratives of the past and inform collective demands towards the future.

Figure 2. Indigenous authorities of the Uru of Lake Poopó visit the National Archive of Bolivia, August 2023 (photograph by the author).

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